

Effect of MRP on yield. Mangalore, India, 1983-85.

Treatment	Yield (kg/plot)		
	1983	1984	1985
<i>Main plot</i>			
Application on day of transplanting	3.72	0.97	1.96
7 DBT	3.89	1.11	2.07
14 DBT	3.71	1.22	1.97
21 DBT	3.71	1.08	1.95
F test	ns	ns	ns
SEm ±	0.10	0.08	0.03
CV (%)	10.62	27.73	5.74
<i>Subplot</i>			
0 kg P/ha	3.10	1.13	1.89
13.2 kg P/ha	3.77	1.11	1.97
26.4 kg P/ha	4.46	1.09	2.07
39.6 kg P/ha	3.83	1.04	2.03
F test ^a	**	ns	**
SEm ±	0.10	0.05	0.02
CV (%)	10.59	17.58	4.50
Interaction (main × sub)	ns	ns	ns

^a*** = significant at 1% level, ns = not significant.

conducted during kharif seasons 1983-85. Experimental site soils are yellowish brown (10 YR 7/6 dry), clay loam, strong medium subangular blocky, dry hard, moist firm, wet sticky, moderately slow permeability with pH 5.7. They are high in organic C (1.26%) and available P (82 kg/ha), but low in available K (50 kg/ha).

Four main treatments (application at 0, 7, 14, and 21 d before transplanting [DBT]) and 4 subtreatments (0, 13.2, 26.4, and 39.6 kg P/ha) were tested in a split-plot design. All plots received 100 kg N and 73 kg K/ha.

Net plot (5.76 m²) yields over a period of 3 yr are presented in the table. Although the yield increase with MRP applied 7 DBT was not significant, the yield difference with 26.4 kg P/ha was significant. The interaction between P level and time of application was not significant. □

Weed seedlings transplanted with rice seedlings reduce grain yield

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We observed that grass weed seedlings had been transplanted with rice

seedlings in two farmers' fields in Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. We harvested 50 1-m² quadrats from areas in both fields where transplanted seedlings were contaminated with weed seedlings and 50 1-m² quadrats from areas where no weed seedlings had been transplanted.

In 1 field, yield from quadrats where an average of 29% of the hills were infested with *Echinochloa glabrescens*

was 372 g/m²; in areas where no weed seedlings were transplanted, the yield was 476 g/m². In the other field, yield from quadrats where an average 23% of the hills were infested with *Echinochloa oryzoides* was 434 g/m², 18% lower than the 530 g/m² yield where no infestation was observed.

Differences in yield between the weed-infested and weed-free hills were highly significant in both fields. □

Nitrogen sources and placement for irrigated rice

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We studied N source and placement method for irrigated rice on a clay loam soil with pH 8.3 and 0.6% organic matter.

Deep placement of urea supergranules (USG) gave a higher yield and was the

most efficient, but was not significantly different from incorporating urea in dry soil (see table). Efficiency of dry soil incorporation was on a par with deep placement of USG

Incorporating urea in puddled soil gave a significantly lower yield. Calcium ammonium nitrate incorporated in puddled soil had the lowest yield after control and was the least efficient. Yields were significantly higher with higher levels of fertilizer but fertilizer efficiency was higher at lower levels. □

Rice grain yield (variety IR6) and fertilizer efficiency as affected by different N sources and their methods of placement. Islamabad, Pakistan, 1982.

Treatment ^a	Grain yield ^b (t/ha)	Fertilizer efficiency (kg yield/kg N used)
Control	3.2 f	—
46 kg N/ha as urea incorporated in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	5.0 d	41.2
46 kg N/ha as calcium ammonium nitrate incorporated in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	4.6 e	30.9
46 kg N/ha as urea all incorporated in dry soil ^c	5.6 c	53.5
46 kg N/ha as USG deep placed, 4 DT	5.6 c	54.2
92 kg N/ha as urea incorporated in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	5.6 c	26.4
92 kg N/ha as calcium ammonium nitrate applied in puddled soil (2/3 basal + 1/3 at PI)	5.1 d	21.7
92 kg N/ha as urea all incorporated in dry soil ^c	6.4 ab	35.7
92 kg N/ha as USG deep placed, 4 DT	6.6 a	37.6
SE	1.1	—

^aPI = panicle initiation, DT = days after transplanting. ^bMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level of significance by DMRT. ^cThe field was irrigated and planted after dry soil incorporation.

Phosphorus application in acid-sulfate soil

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In the Cuu Long (Mekong) Delta of Vietnam, acid-sulfate soils are found in 1.15 million ha, mostly in Kien Giang, Long An, Dong Thap, Hau Giang, and An Giang Provinces. Seedling mortality and poor crop growth due to extremely